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MADRASAH EDUCATION PROGRAM IN TARLAC CITY, PHILIPPINES

A Thesis Presented
To the Faculty of the Graduate School
Osias Colleges, Inc.
Tarlac City

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree
Master of Arts in Education
Major in Administration and Supervision

ALMAIRA H. MOUMEN

December 2023

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ABSTRACT

Title: **MADRASAH EDUCATION PROGRAM IN TARLAC, CITY PHILIPPINES**

Researcher: **ALMAIRA H. MOUMEN**

Degree: **MASTER OF ARTS IN EDUCATION**

Major: **ADMINISTRATION AND SUPERVISION**

Institution: **OSIAS COLLEGES, INC.**

The study examined the Madrasah Elementary Education Curriculum in Tarlac City, Philippines using the quantitative research approach. The respondents were the Division Supervisor, Alive Coordinators in Sto. Cristo Integrated School, San Isidro, Tibag, Northern Hill Elementary School Annex and twenty-nine (29) pupils as participants whose performance was determined. A validated survey questionnaire was used to evaluate the MADRASAH Curriculum.

The Arabic Language had an average of Very Satisfactory while for the Islamic Values, 3 schools had Outstanding pupils and the rest were rated very satisfactory. The current study found out that the MADRASAH Curriculum in Tarlac City was described as EXCELLENT in all aspect; Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness, Quality of Educational Content, Teacher Preparedness and Training, Inclusivity and Diversity, Student Engagement and Support, Integration with National Educational Framework and Assessment and Evaluation Process. Enhanced Opportunities for improvement were proposed to promote continuous growth allowing all stakeholders to explore new experiences and learn new skills for better outcomes.

In view of the conclusions, it is recommended that the proposed enhancement opportunity plan should be implemented. The said plan will not only help teachers (Asatidz) but also stakeholders of the school. It is also recommended that all stakeholders be aware in the changes and updates in madrasah Curriculum Implementation. This Proposed enhancement Opportunity Plan will be a good start in strengthening the curriculum implementation.

Keywords: *Asatidz, Madrasah Curriculum, Islamic Values*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education is crucial in determining the destiny of both individuals and communities in an age of growing globalization and cultural diversity. The Madrasah education programs are crucial institutions for transferring Arabic language and Islamic values to the Muslim population in Tarlac City, where cultural and religious diversity is a defining characteristic. These Madaris are in charge of not only educating the next generation but also safeguarding and advancing Islamic culture and identity.

All types of educational delivery systems are invited to join the worldwide Education for Education for All (EFA) pledge to provide access to high-quality education. Quality education opportunities must be provided to all children, regardless of their race, color, religion, or culture (EFA Goals).

In relation with the EFA, in 1996 Peace agreement, the teaching of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education is declared a vital component of the National Educational System through DepEd Order No. 51, s. 2004. The Muslim Education Roadmap was conceptualized to respond to the relevant provisions of the President's 10-point agenda under the medium term Philippine Development Plan and the Expanded Organic Act for Muslim Mindanao. It aims to positively contribute to the ongoing peace process and to enhance educational development of Filipino Muslims through an Islamic-friendly public education system that seeks to improve the quality of life of Muslim school children.

The foundation of the educational system is the Madrasah curriculum, which determines what knowledge and values are taught to the pupils. It is crucial to routinely assess the curriculum of the Madrasah education program in Tarlac City to make sure that it is efficient and responsive to the demands of the Muslim community. This review procedure will reveal the advantages and disadvantages of the current curriculum, point out areas that need to be improved, and eventually raise the standard of instruction given to Madrasah students.

The importance of Madrasah education for the Filipino Muslims and the problems of mainstreaming it to the larger national system of education were first noted during the Martial Law years. Perhaps, the Moro rebellion in the early 1970's might have forced the government attention on the importance of Madrasah education.

Madrasah education in the Philippines is primarily associated with the Muslim minority population, particularly in the southern regions like Mindanao. It is designed to provide Islamic education and teachings alongside the regular curriculum. Madrasah education has a long history in the Philippines, dating back to the pre-colonial period when Islamic culture and education were present in various parts of the archipelago. However, its formalization and integration into the national education system came much later. In the late 20th century, there were efforts to integrate Madrasah education into the national educational framework. The government recognized the need to provide quality education for Muslim Filipinos and to ensure that Madrasah graduates have access to mainstream education and employment opportunities. The ARMM played a significant role in the development of Madrasah education in the region. It worked to establish Madrasah education centers, train teachers, and improve the curriculum.

The Department of Education (DepEd) initiated the Madrasah Education Program, which aimed to improve the quality of Madrasah education and integrate it into the national education system. This program included the development of a standardized curriculum. The

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Madrasah curriculum typically includes Islamic studies, Arabic language, and other core subjects similar to the regular curriculum in Philippine public schools. It aims to provide students with a well-rounded education that incorporates both Islamic teachings and general knowledge. While there are standardized guidelines for Madrasah education, there may be local variations in how the curriculum is implemented, depending on the specific Madrasah and its location.

Many educators in Lanao del Sur and Marawi City during the term of President Marcos, several Letters of Instruction (LOI) were issued mandating integration of Madrasah into Philippine system of education, and authorized the use of Arabic language as a medium of instruction in Arabic subjects among the basic education institutions in the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM). However, as the late Dr. Salipada Tamano has pronounced on many occasions that these efforts to mainstream madrasah education were not extremely successful. Accordingly, during the term of former President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo, she has made a different approach, a low-key approach by appointing Muslim leaders one after another. To name a few we have Madam Sandra Sema and Atty. Macapanton Abbas Jr., their appointment mandate was to upgrade the quality of Muslim basic education, including the mainstreaming of Madrasah education as a component of the national system of education.

Madrasah education in the Philippines, including Tarlac City, is primarily associated with Muslim communities and aims to provide Islamic education alongside the regular curriculum. Please note that educational policies and programs may evolve over time, so I recommend checking with local educational authorities or institutions in Tarlac City for the most up-to-date information on Madrasah curriculum in the area. Madaris in the Philippines typically offer courses in Islamic studies. These courses cover topics such as the Quran, Hadith (sayings and actions of the Prophet Muhammad), Islamic jurisprudence, Islamic history, and other aspects of Islamic knowledge and faith.

In addition to Islamic studies and Arabic language instruction, Madaris may also offer a regular curriculum that includes subjects like Mathematics, Science, English, and Social Studies. This is to ensure that students receive a well-rounded education and have the option to pursue higher education or careers outside of religious studies. Madrasah education also focuses on cultural sensitivity and understanding among students, promoting respect for different cultures and religions. The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has been working to integrate Madrasah education into the national education system. The DepEd's Madrasah Education Program aims to standardize and improve the quality of Madrasah education across the country.

But the actual design and development to mainstreamed, Madrasah education started only in the early 2002 at the initiative of DepEd-ARMM former Regional Secretary, the late Dr. Mahid M. Mutilan. The effort began with the conduct of consultative conference on the design of curriculum for Madrasah Education. Subsequently, Dr. Mutilan issued DepEd ARMM Order No.1, s, 2002, creating the Project of Madrasah Education (PME) with the mandate to design and develop the Madrasah Curriculum.

In August 2004, former DepEd Secretary Edilberto de Jesus authorized the conduct of seminar/workshop on the preparation and unification of MADARIS Education. The participants were representatives of different organizations that started to work on the design of the curriculum. The final output of the workshop was the basis of DepEd Order No. 51, s 2004, prescribing the standard Curriculum for Madrasah Education in the Philippines. Madrasah Education or ALIVE Program was created to provide Muslim children in the ARMM with quality

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education that is responsive to their needs to acquire knowledge and skills, with values anchored on the Islamic faith to prepare them for further learning and challenges in society today. (Madrasah Education (2011, March 7).

Moreover, the refined Elementary Madrasah Curriculum, popularly known as ALIVE is the heart of the program. May Allāh honor him and grant him peace.": *sallā llāhu 'alay-hi wa-sallam* - S. A. W., SAAW, or SAAS) - this expression follows specifically after uttering the name of Muhammad, although "peace be upon him" may be used instead.

The ALIVE Program aims to develop the spiritual, moral, lingual, mental and physical capabilities among Muslim students. The first completers of level 6 graduated last March 2014. Various activities were also introduced to enhance the program, like celebration of Muslim Holidays e.g. Eid'l Ft'r and Eid'l Adha. Benchmarking to an Islamic School and other public schools who are implementers of the Program was conducted by School officials to improve the implementation.

It is believed that its implementation has been beneficial not only to the pupils but to the community as well. Muslim culture is enriched through the program. At present, the division has 3 Asatidz, one of whom is an Education graduate but not yet LET Passer and in temporary status.

It is crucial that the Madrasah education program develops along with Tarlac City's ongoing evolution and embrace of diversity. This assessment is an important step in ensuring that Tarlac City's madrasahs continue to offer high-quality instruction while conserving the diverse cultural and religious traditions of the Muslim community. By reviewing the curriculum, we seek to support continuing initiatives to help Madrasah students develop into well-rounded individuals capable of thriving in a fast-paced, globally connected environment.

Tarlac City Division is hoping that this program will contribute meaningfully not only to the peace efforts of the government but to come up with competent Muslim pupils who are speaking Arabic Language and practicing Islamic Values for a better Philippines.

It is a program to guide public elementary schools and private Madaris in the planning, teaching and assessing of Islamic Studies (including Islamic Values Education) and Arabic language within the context of the Philippines education. It provides for an enriched teaching curriculum for public schools as Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education are taught in addition to subjects in the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) (Refined Elementary Madrasah Curriculum, 2014).

The Madrasah Curriculum is already embraced by Tarlac City's Department of Education Division because many Muslims have already immigrated and settled there. There are four school implementers of Madrasah Education Program in Tarlac City. The Sto. Cristo Integrated School that started by the year 2008, San Isidro Elementary School since 2017, Tibag Elementary School since 2018, and Northern Hill Elementary School Annex since 2019. The proportion of Muslim pupils has already increased. Madaris are already being implemented in schools to meet the educational demands of Muslim students and provide them with all the resources they require to learn their distinct religions.

This study is primarily aimed at investigating the level of effectiveness of the implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education and the problems encountered in teaching ALIVE. The success of this study would help Islamize the learners knowledge that will make them knowledgeable of the Holy Qur'an and the Hadith of the Prophet Muhammad (S. A. W) and hopefully will make the learners emulate the character traits and virtues of Prophet Muhammad (S. A. W) as God-fearing, nationalistic, law abiding,

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with concern for his fellowmen and the environment, knowledgeable in Arabic, intelligent and industrious and learners that lives up to expectations.

Tarlac City has a number of Muslim migrants from Mindanao and also some converts evident by their mosque, enrolment of Muslim learners in public and private schools, market vendors and other business establishment owned by them. The ALIVE program started in school year 2008-2009 in Sto. Cristo Elementary School as the pilot school. It is now on its 8th year of implementation.

Prior to its implementation, a lot of preparations were made. Such as attending training and seminar on the program, school mapping, meeting with the Muslim communities and linkage with the Local Government Unit for funding support.

The program includes additional two subjects to the regular curriculum. These are Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (acronym ALIVE). The learners should finish 6 levels or 6 grade level to complete the program in the elementary. Each level has a different set of competencies. During the first year of implementation, it started with 68 enrollees, the program requires only a minimum of 15. The first batch of completers in 2013-2014 receive certificate of completion in addition to their elementary diploma. It has 172 enrollees this school year.

Challenges were met along the way its implementation. Some of them include, absenteeism, dropping out of pupils due to transfer of residence, delayed honorarium of teachers, lack of classroom, inadequate competencies of some Asatidz (Muslim Teachers) because they are not education graduates and have contractual status, scarcity of qualified asatidz. At present, there is only one hired permanent Muslim teacher.

Interventions were made to improve the program. Teachers are sent to training for competency enhancement. Benchmarking to other Muslim schools are organized to inspire them as well as to emulate good practices. Muslim holidays are celebrated in the school not only for the Muslim learners but also to educate non-Muslim on the Muslim culture. It is also a way of developing friendship and camaraderie between Muslim and Christians. Teachers do home visits to those pupils at risk of dropping out. Technical assistance on classroom management and teaching strategies are rendered to them by the principal and supervisors. They are also included in the faculty meetings and other school programs.

Immersion in the program is a meaningful experience. Some of the gains we can be proud of will include the following: gradually bridging cultural differences between Muslims and Christians, learning the Muslim culture, Job opportunity for asatidz/ Muslim teachers, gaining Muslim friends, brotherhood, and seeing learners who can speak Arabic language and practice Islamic values.

This study was primarily investigated the level of effectiveness of the implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education and the problems encountered in teaching ALIVE. The success of this study would help Islamize the learners knowledge that will make them knowledgeable of the Holy Qur'an and the Hadith of the Prophet Muhammad (S. A. W) and hopefully would make the learners emulate the character traits and virtues of Prophet Muhammad (S. A. W) as God-fearing, nationalistic, law abiding, with concern for his fellowmen and the environment, knowledgeable in Arabic, intelligent and industrious and learners that lives up to expectations.

Statement Of The Problem

The aim of the study was to evaluate the Madrasah Educational Curriculum in Tarlac City. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. How is the performance of the ALIVE learners described in terms of:

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- 1.1. Arabic Language; and
- 1.2. Islamic Values?
2. How is the Madrasah Education Curriculum implementation described along:
 - 2.1. Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness;
 - 2.2. Quality of Educational Content
 - 2.3. Teacher Preparedness and Training;
 - 2.4. Inclusivity and Diversity;
 - 2.5. Student Engagement and Support;
 - 2.6. Integration with National Educational Framework; and
 - 2.7. Assessment and Evaluation Practices?
3. What enhancement opportunities could be proposed for a better preparation of the students to meet the challenges in preserving Islamic values and traditions?

Theoretical Framework

Applying Social Learning Theory to Madrasah implementation in Tarlac City involves understanding how social interactions, modeling, and observational learning shape educational practices and influence the adoption of Madrasah education within the community. Teachers, community leaders, and parents serve as models for students. Their behaviors and attitudes toward Madrasah education significantly influence students' perceptions and acceptance. Highlighting successful individuals who have benefited from Madrasah education can positively impact students' attitudes and motivate their engagement. Designing Madrasah classrooms to promote group discussions, cooperative projects, and peer learning opportunities enhances social interactions and knowledge sharing among students. Involving the broader community in educational activities fosters collective learning experiences beyond the classroom. Establishing a community of practice among Madrasah teachers, parents, and community leaders fosters a supportive environment for sharing knowledge and best practices. Encouraging continuous professional development for Madrasah educators promotes the exchange of innovative teaching methods and educational strategies. Integrating teachings that emphasize cooperation, empathy, and mutual respect aligns with Social Learning Theory and fosters a positive and inclusive learning environment. Teaching conflict resolution techniques within the Madrasah curriculum equips students with essential social skills. Employing observational methods to assess students' social interactions, collaborative skills, and adherence to positive behavioral models. Providing feedback to students, educators, and the community regarding the observed impacts of social learning strategies on Madrasah education. Employing observational methods to assess students' social interactions, collaborative skills, and adherence to positive behavioral models.

Applying Social Learning Theory in the context of Madrasah implementation in Tarlac City involves creating an environment that fosters positive social interactions, encourages modeling of desirable behaviors, and leverages community involvement to support the adoption and success of Madrasah education.

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Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

The evaluation of the curriculum in the Madrasah Education Program in Tarlac City should provide a structured overview of the key elements, relationships, and factors involved in the evaluation process.

Based on the figure above, for the successful implementation of the Madrasah Curriculum, the main goal of this study is to evaluate the whole Madrasah Curriculum based on: (1) Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness, (2) Quality of Educational Content, (3) Teacher Preparedness and Training ;(4) Inclusivity and Diversity; (5) Student Engagement and Support; (6) Integration with National Educational Framework; and (7) Assessment and Evaluation Practices.

This conceptual framework provides a structured approach to evaluating the Madrasah curriculum in Tarlac City, taking into account the contextual factors, curriculum inputs, implementation processes, learning outcomes, stakeholder involvement, the evaluation process, continuous improvement, and the broader impact on students and the community.

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METHODS

Research Design

The study employed the quantitative method using the descriptive research design.. This allows the researcher for a more holistic understanding of the curriculum and its impact.

According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. It can use a wide variety to investigate one or more variables. It does not control or manipulate any of the variables, but only observes and measures them.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in four (4) schools in Tarlac City where the MADRASAH Curriculum is implemented among Muslim learners.

The Tarlac City Schools Division started offering Madrasah Education to Muslim pupils starting this school year 2008-2009. It has a total of 72 Muslim Pupils in the elementary and 4 students in the secondary. The DepED Regional Office has a pool of qualified Muslim Teachers who are trained in teaching Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education. However, DepED-Madrasah is only giving a matching fund P2,500.00 per teacher. In the year 2008, the enrollees in Sto. Cristo Elementary School, where the school was first implemented, were 68 pupils. In the school year 2009-2010, the enrollees decreased to 45 pupils. By the school year 2010-2011, the enrollees started to increase, compared to the previous school year, and became 75 pupils.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study, are the Division Supervisor, ALIVE Coordinators, and Teachers in Sto. Cristo Integrated School, San Isidro Elementary School, Tibag Elementary School, and Northern Hill Elementary School Annex under the ALIVE curriculum program in the Department of Education –Division of Tarlac City. It included a total of twenty nine (29) elementary pupils, whose performance was determined. The number of enrollees in Madrasah Education continuously increased as it became 104 pupils in the school year 2013-2014. Still continues growing and became 123 pupils in the school year 2014-2015. As the urge in this curriculum continuously growing, from one school implementer there are now four schools that offer the Madrasah Curriculum in Division of Tarlac City, namely –Sto. Cristo Integrated School (the first implementer), San Isidro Elementary School, Tibag Elementary School, and Northern Hill Elementary School Annex.

Research Instrument

Questionnaire was used as the instrument to gather the necessary data in the study.

The questionnaire intends to evaluate the implementation of the Madrasah Education Curriculum in terms of Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness; Quality of Educational Content; Teacher Preparedness; Quality of Educational Content; Teacher Preparedness and Training; Inclusivity and Diversity; Student Engagement and Support; Integration with National Educational Framework; and Assessment and Evaluation Practices.

The questionnaire was evaluated by the Dean of the Graduate School and the chief of Curriculum Implementation Division (CID) of the Division of Tarlac City.

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Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher administered the structured surveys to students, teachers, coordinators, supervisors, parents, and community members to collect quantitative data on their perceptions, satisfaction, and opinions regarding the curriculum. The assessment result on the academic performance of the pupils was based from their permanent records.

It was followed by the qualitative data collection through the semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, including Madrasah administrators, teachers, and community leaders, to explore their perspectives, experiences, and recommendations regarding the curriculum. Focus group discussions were organized with students to gain insights from their experiences with the curriculum, challenges they face, and suggestions for improvement.

Statistical Analysis

The grading system to determine the academic performance of the Madrasah pupils is based from DepEd Order #8, s. 2015 as follows,

1. On Academic Performance

Grades	Description
90-100	Outstanding
85-89	Very Satisfactory
80-84	Satisfactory
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectation

2. The scoring protocol used to describe the curriculum:

Index	Limits Of Index	Verbal Description	Interpretation
4	3.5 – 4.0	Strongly Agree	Excellent
3	2.5 – 3.49	Agree	Very Good
2	1.5 – 2.49	Disagree	Good
1	1.0 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Poor

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Madrasah Educational Curriculum has been implemented in Tarlac City Division for almost one decade and a half for which this study is interested to present its present status.

3.1 Academic Performance

This part gives focus on the academic performance of the students under the Madrasah Curriculum Education Program in Tarlac City. Comprehending academic achievement is essential because it sheds light on the specific elements affecting students' learning experiences as well as the efficacy of instructional strategies. The academic performance was based on the grades they acquire for the last school year. This was based on the criteria needed in learning the competencies relevant to the Values. The grades of the students were categorized pursuant to Deped Order No. 8, s. 2015 into five, namely: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

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3.1. Arabic Language

The Arabic language holds a significant place in the curriculum of Madrasah Educational Program. The Arabic language stands as the cornerstone of Islamic education in madrasahs around the world. Its importance lies not only in being the language of the Quran, the holy book of Islam, but also in its historical and cultural significance within the Islamic faith. In madrasahs, the study of Arabic encompasses various aspects, including grammar, syntax, literature, and linguistics (Al-Ebady, A., 2018). Students delve into the intricacies of classical Arabic to comprehend religious texts, scholarly works, and traditions that have been passed down through generations. Understanding Arabic is crucial for Muslims seeking a deeper connection to their faith. Proficiency in the language enables students to directly access the primary sources of Islam, allowing them to interpret and analyze religious texts with accuracy and depth. The inclusion of Arabic as a subject in madrasahs is fundamental not only for religious purposes but also for preserving cultural heritage and fostering a holistic education that connects students with the language and essence of Islam (Duderija, A., & Rane, H., 2019).

Table 1 Arabic Language

Description	Frequency				FREQUENCY	Percentage (%)
	San Isidro Elem School	Tibag Elem	Sto. Cristo Elem	Northern Hill		
Outstanding (90-100)		2	6	2	10	34.48
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	2	3	5	2	12	41.38
Satisfactory (80-84)	1	4	1		6	20.69
Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)		1			1	3.45
Did not Meet Expectation (74below)						0
Total	3	10	12	4	29	100

The table above shows that the pupils in different grade levels came from the four (4) schools in Tarlac City Division, namely; San Isidro Elementary School, Tibag Elementary School, Sto. Cristo Elementary School, and Northern Hill Elementary School Annex. There are a total of twenty nine (29) pupils from grade five (5) in Sto. Cristo, San Isidro, and Tibag Elementary School including 2 grade two (2) pupils in Northern Hill. Based on their academic performance in Arabic Language, 1 or 3.45% of them got a fairly satisfactory grade ranges from 75-79. Six or 20.69 of them are under satisfactory who got grades ranges 80-84. Twelve of the students or 41.38% got a Very Satisfactory rating that ranges from 85-89. Lastly, the remaining ten students or 34.48% of the respondents got a grades ranges from 90-100.

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Based on the statement of Gilman (2010), Arabic is the main language of Islam, a religion that has around 1.5 billion followers. It is the language of the Quran that is read and studied by all Muslims. Muslims also need Arabic to perform prayers and other forms of worship. (According to Tan (2009), The introduction of the Madrasah education system in the Philippines is part of a broader effort across Southeast Asia to provide quality education to Muslim students while preserving their religious and cultural identity. The Philippine government, through the Department of Education, has been actively promoting the integration of Madrasah education into the public school system to ensure that Muslim children receive an inclusive and well-rounded education. Additionally, it was said by Kawangit (2015), The Arabic Language (ALIVE) Program is the result of the dedicated efforts of the Department of Education Central, Regional and Division officials and Asatidz (teachers) who believe in the worth and development potential of every Muslim child in multi-cultural and diverse environment. The main objective of this is the unity and harmony in Muslim-Christian relationship.

Arabic is the main language utilized because the curriculum is centered on the madrasah. It is undeniably true that learning the language is a smart idea before delving further into any given culture. It is evident that students following Tarlac City's Madrasah Curriculum began studying Arabic in order to enhance their education under the curriculum.

3.1.2. Islamic Values

The teaching of Islamic values in madrasahs plays a pivotal role in shaping the moral compass and character development of students. Islamic values are the ethical and moral principles derived from the teachings of Islam, serving as guiding lights in the lives of Muslims (Halstead, J. M., 2004). In madrasahs, the subject of Islamic values forms the bedrock of education, aiming to instill virtues, ethics, and principles that align with Islamic teachings. The subject goes beyond theoretical knowledge; it is a practical application of the core principles that define Islam. Students delve into the teachings of the Quran and Hadith, the sayings and actions of Prophet Muhammad, to understand and internalize values such as compassion, justice, honesty, humility, and empathy (Hussain, S., 2007). Madrasahs emphasize the importance of integrating these values into daily life, fostering a holistic approach to education. Through various teachings, discussions, and examples from Islamic history, students learn to apply these values in their personal conduct, interactions with others, and decision-making processes. The study of Islamic values in Madaris serves as a compass, guiding students in navigating the complexities of the modern world while staying rooted in their faith. It encourages critical thinking, moral reasoning, and the development of a strong ethical foundation that shapes individuals into responsible and contributing members of society. The inclusion of Islamic values as a subject in madrasahs is integral to the holistic development of individuals, nurturing not just intellectual growth but also moral and ethical maturity, ensuring they become exemplary individuals who contribute positively to their communities and the world at large (Zaman, M. Q., 2002).

These values encompass various aspects of personal conduct, social interactions, and spiritual growth. They are not merely religious precepts but also moral and ethical standards that influence the daily lives of over a billion people worldwide. Faith is the foundation of Islamic values. It involves belief in the oneness of God (Allah), the prophethood of Muhammad, the existence of angels, the revealed books, the Day of Judgment, and divine predestination. This belief system shapes a Muslim's worldview and provides a sense of purpose and direction.

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Table 2. Islamic Values

Description	Frequency				FREQUENCY	Percentage
	San Isidro Elem School	Tibag Elem	Sto. Cristo Elem	Northern Hills		
Outstanding		4	6	2	12	41.38
Very Satisfactory	3	1	6	2	12	41.38
Satisfactory		4			4	13.79
Fairly Satisfactory		1			1	3.45
Did not Meet Expectation						0
Total	3	10	12	4	29	100

The table above shows that the pupils in different grade levels who came from four (4) schools in Tarlac City Division, namely; San Isidro Elementary School, Tibag Elementary School, Sto. Cristo Elementary School, and Northern Hill Elementary School Annex. There are a total of twenty nine (29) pupils in schools given under the Madrasah Curriculum Program in Elementary Level. Based on their academic performance in Islamic Values, 1 or 3.45% of them got a fairly satisfactory grade ranges from 75-79. Four or 13.79% of them are under satisfactory who got grades ranges 80-84. Twelve of the students or 41.38% got a Very Satisfactory rating that ranges from 85-89. Lastly, the remaining twelve students or 41.38% of the respondents got a grades ranges from 90-100.

According to the article of Muhamat (2018), the implementation of Islamic Values Education Program in public schools is something new in the society. However, there are some writing like Cesar Adib Majul (1978) in his 12 pages of mimeographed paper entitled 'The Problems of Islamic Education at the University Level in the Philippines'. This study discussed about brief overview of Islamic education from the centuries of maktab to the emergence of Pandita schools' and Madaris up to the establishment of the King Faisal Center at Mindanao State University and the Institute of Islamic Studies at the University of the Philippines.

It is beneficial to concentrate on the Islamic values that are taught in the Alive Program after taking into account the terminology employed in the implementation of the Madrasah curriculum. The Islamic Values are used to provide a more thorough overview of Islamic values.

3.2 The Evaluation of Madrasah Elementary Education Curriculum

The evaluation of the Madrasah Elementary Education Curriculum is a critical undertaking aimed at assessing its effectiveness in providing a comprehensive and holistic education to young learners. Charity is a fundamental value in Islam. Muslims are required to give a portion of their wealth to the less fortunate, promoting social justice and economic equity. This practice fosters a sense of community and responsibility towards others. This curriculum is designed not only to impart basic academic skills but also to integrate Islamic values and teachings, fostering both intellectual and moral development. As Madaris play a pivotal role in shaping the educational landscape in many Muslim communities, evaluating their curriculum is essential to ensure that it meets the evolving educational needs and adheres

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to the highest standards of quality and relevance. This study seeks to explore the strengths and areas for improvement within the Madrasah Elementary Education Curriculum, providing insights that can inform future curriculum development and implementation strategies.

3.2.1 Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness

According to Abdullah (2003), curriculum relevance and responsiveness in Madrasah Education Program ensures that the educational content aligns with need of the students, society, and the changing global landscape. This likely includes incorporating Islamic studies alongside standards subjects, adapting curricula to local contexts, and addressing contemporary issues. The Madrasah Education Program in the Philippines integrates Islamic studies with the regular academic curriculum. This ensures that students receive a holistic education that includes both religious and secular knowledge (DepEd Order No. 51, s. 2004).

Table 3. Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
The curriculum is aligned with current industry trends and prepares students for the demands.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The curriculum is flexible and adaptable to accommodate diverse learning styles and needs.	3.82	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The curriculum includes real-world applications and practical skills that are relevant to students' future careers.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The curriculum encourages critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity among students.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The curriculum is responsive to the changing needs and expectations of students, employers, and society.	3.45	Agree	Very Good
Grand Mean	3.60	Strongly Agree	Excellent

Table 3 shows the evaluation of Madrasah Curriculum in the aspect of Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness. Specifically, respondents agreed that the curriculum is responsive to the changing needs and expectations of students, employers, and society. ($\bar{x}=3.55$) that shown a very good interpretation. Moreover, the respondents strongly agreed on the excellence of the curriculum alignment with the current industry trends and prepares students for the demand, ($\bar{x}=3.64$), the flexibility and adaptability of the curriculum in accommodating diverse learning styles and needs ($\bar{x}=3.82$), the inclusion of real-world applications and practical skills which is relevant to the future careers of the students ($\bar{x}=3.55$), and lastly, the curriculum encourages critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity among students ($\bar{x}=3.55$). Overall, the Madrasah Curriculum on Curriculum Relevance and responsiveness shows excellence ($\bar{x}=3.60$).

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According to Ameyaw (2016), In order to meet the ever-evolving needs of students, a curriculum that is responsive must bridge the gap between theories and general knowledge and the contextual, ever-changing realities of daily life and the workplace. The curriculum must now be flexible and adaptive to meet current demands, such as those in the workplace, rather than being uniform and set for extended periods of time. It must be connected to each learner's specific needs while also considering the difficulties and expectations faced by practitioners and foreseeing emerging trends. The need for "relevant, flexible, diverse, and integrated" curricula in order to equip graduates of today with the skills they will need to face difficulties in the future. It was also added that the term "responsive curriculum" describes a flexible and adaptable curriculum that, on the one hand, bridges the gap between abstract ideas of education, learning, and universal knowledge and the more demanding, contextual, and ever-changing realities of daily life and the workplace.

In the Division of Tarlac City, which implements Madrasah Curriculum, the curriculum is yearly updated to align with the current trends and advancement of technology through seminar workshop hosted by the Division office. The Madrasah Curriculum, like any educational program, must evolve to remain relevant and effective in preparing students for the future. Implementers of the said curriculum, incorporate to focus holistic development – such as Socio-emotional learning that focus on student's emotional intelligence development, resilience, and interpersonal skills, needs of the students with the latest skills –such as Digital Literacy that includes understanding how to deal with systems, and knowledge demanded globally. Educating students about global issues, such as economic trends, political developments, and international relations, prepares them to be informed and active global citizens.

3.2.2. Quality of Educational Content

The quality education in Madrasah Education Program is essential for providing a well-rounded and effective experience. This likely involves developing curricula that are aligned with educational standards, integrating Islamic studies, ensuring balance between religious and secular subjects. The content should be engaging, culturally relevant, and cater to the diverse needs of students. The quality education in the Madrasah Education Program is essential for providing a well-rounded and effective experience. This likely involves developing curricula that are aligned with educational standards, integrating Islamic studies, and ensuring a balance between religious and secular subjects. The content should be engaging, culturally relevant, and cater to the diverse needs of students (Hashim, R., 2014).

Table 4. Quality of Educational Content

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
The educational content is engaging and holds my interest throughout the learning experience.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The educational materials are well-organized and easy to follow, enhancing my understanding of the subject matter.	3.36	Agree	Very Good

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The educational content is up-to-date and reflects current knowledge and best practices in the field.	3.45	Agree	Very Good
The educational content provides practical and real-world applications of the concepts learned.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The educational content is inclusive and respects diversity, reflecting different perspectives and backgrounds.	3.73	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Grand Mean	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent

Table 4 shows the evaluation of Madrasah Curriculum in terms of Quality of Educational content. Specifically, the respondents agreed that the educational materials are well-organized and easy to follow ($\bar{x}=3.36$) and the educational content is updated to current knowledge and best practices in the field ($\bar{x}=3.45$). Moreover, the respondents strongly agreed that the quality of educational content is engaging and continuously holds their interest through learning experiences ($\bar{x}=3.55$) described as excellent. Likewise, it provides practical and real world concepts ($\bar{x}=3.64$), and it is inclusive and gives respect in diversity ($\bar{x}=3.73$). Overall, the Madrasah Curriculum shoes excellence in quality of Educational content ($\bar{x}=3.55$).

According to Tan (2009), The integration of Islamic studies with secular subjects aims to provide a balanced education that caters to the spiritual and intellectual needs of students. Studies have shown that this integration helps maintain students' cultural and religious identity while equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge for modern society. The Madrasah Education Program in the Philippines has evolved from traditional Islamic schools into a more structured and formalized system integrated within the national education framework. This evolution aims to provide Muslim students with an education that respects their cultural and religious backgrounds while meeting national educational standards. Ismail (2015) also added that the Madrasah Education Program emphasizes a balanced curriculum that integrates Islamic studies with secular subjects. This holistic approach ensures that students receive comprehensive education that respects their cultural and religious backgrounds while meeting academic standards.

The Department of Education (DepEd) Division of Tarlac City assures that the curriculum implementation of Madrasah Curriculum Program gives a quality education among the Muslim students. It assures the alignment of content in the National Based Curriculum which is delivered among the Muslim students. The implementers assure that the curriculum content is engaging, well-organized, up-to-date, and practical. The educational materials are effective in meeting the learner's expectations across various aspect of content quality and delivery. Through incorporating authentic learning experiences that allow students to apply their knowledge in a real-world context. Students participate in activity like hands-on activity in making Islamic Values authentic.

3.2.3 Teacher Preparedness and Training

According to Gorres (2014), teacher preparedness and training in Madrasah Education Program likely involve equipping educators with necessary skills and knowledge to effectively teach in a diverse and inclusive setting. This may include specialized training in Islamic studies,

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pedagogical, methods and cultural sensitivity to ensure that teachers can provide quality education while understanding and respecting the religious and cultural background of their students. The effectiveness of teaching is significantly influenced by the level of preparedness and the quality of training that educators receive. Well-prepared teachers are better equipped to implement innovative instructional strategies, adapt to diverse learning styles, and create inclusive classroom environments.

Table 5 Teacher's Preparedness and Training

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Teachers at this institution are well-prepared and knowledgeable in their subject matter.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The professional development opportunities provided to teachers are effective in enhancing their teaching skills and knowledge.	3.73	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Teachers at this institution receive adequate training and support to effectively integrate technology into their teaching.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Teacher training programs at this institution are responsive to the changing needs of students and the education landscape.	3.27	Agree	Very Good
Teachers regularly engage in professional development activities to stay current in their field and improve their teaching skills.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Grand Mean	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent

Data in table 5 presents the evaluation in Teacher's Preparedness and Training as part of the evaluation in Madrasah Curriculum. Learners under Madrasah Curriculum agreed that the teachers training program are responsive to the changing needs of students and the educational landscape (\bar{x} =3.27) that shows very good. Additionally, the Madrasah Curriculum shows also excellence in having teachers that are well-planned and knowledgeable in their different subject matter (\bar{x} =3.55), teachers who are teaching under Madrasah Curriculum, undergo professional development opportunity to provide teachers effectivity in enhancing their skills and knowledge (\bar{x} =3.73), it also shows that the said curriculum is excellent in receiving teachers adequate training and support to integration of technology into their teaching (\bar{x} =3.64). Lastly, the Madrasah Curriculum shows excellence which pertains to Teachers Preparedness and Training (\bar{x} =3.55).

The importance of teacher preparation and training in educational programs has been extensively documented in the literature. Effective teacher preparation ensures that educators possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and pedagogical strategies to deliver quality instruction (Guskey & Yoon, 2020). Research suggests that well-trained teachers are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of their students and create supportive learning environments (Guskey & Yoon, 2020). Moreover, studies have shown that teacher preparation

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programs that align with curriculum goals and objectives contribute to improved student outcomes (Guskey & Yoon, 2020). Additionally, the significance of ongoing professional development for teachers in implementing curriculum programs has been emphasized in educational research (Guskey & Yoon, 2020).

The DepEd Division of Tarlac City always supports the professional growth and development among the teachers and implementers of Madrasah Curriculum. All the Alive teachers are undergoing trainings and seminars focusing in the professional development of teachers and up to date strategies in teaching to assure the quality education that they give among the Muslim students. The Division of Tarlac City provides numerous trainings to support teaching staff. The preparedness of teachers shows their effectiveness in integration of the current trends. The commitment among teachers is evident on account of their positive view of the institution's philosophy and the support system is in place for their continuous improvement. Some of the trainings of the teachers are focused on modern teaching methodologies and classroom management to ensure effective learning specially when it comes to Madrasah Curriculum.

3.2.4 Inclusivity and Diversity

Inclusivity and Diversity like refers to the promotion of an educational environment that welcomes students from various backgrounds, culture, and beliefs. Inclusivity and diversity are cornerstone principles for building equitable and dynamic communities. To create environments where everyone feels appreciated, respected, and able to contribute completely, inclusivity and diversity are essential. These concepts recognize and celebrate differences among individuals, whether in terms of race, gender, age, religion, sexual orientation, physical abilities, or socioeconomic status. In a world increasingly interconnected and diverse, fostering inclusivity and embracing diversity are essential for societal progress and harmony. The integration of inclusivity and diversity into various settings brings multiple benefits. In educational contexts, it enriches the learning experience by exposing students to a broad spectrum of viewpoints, promoting critical thinking, and preparing them for a diverse world. It may involve ensuring that the curriculum is inclusive, respecting and representing that diversity of students and fostering an atmosphere where everyone feel valued and included in the learning process (Banks, J. A., 2016).

Table 6. Inclusivity and Diversity

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
This institution promotes a welcoming and inclusive environment for individuals of all backgrounds.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Diversity is celebrated and respected within the curriculum and classroom discussions.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Excellent
I feel that my unique background and experiences are valued and included in the learning environment.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent

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Inclusive teaching practices are evident in the classroom, allowing all students to participate and excel.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The institution actively promotes diversity and inclusivity in hiring practices and faculty representation.	3.73	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Grand Mean	3.62	Strongly Agree	Excellent

Data on this table shows the evaluation of Madrasah Curriculum in the aspect of Inclusivity and Diversity. It specifically shows that respondents strongly agree in promoting an inclusive environment for all ($\bar{x}=3.55$), in diversify the curriculum and classroom discussion ($\bar{x}=3.64$), student friendly and all experiences of the learners are valued ($\bar{x}=3.55$), interpreted as Excellent. Moreover, Madrasah practices inclusive teaching which are evident in the classroom ($\bar{x}=3.64$), and schools promotes diversity and inclusivity in hiring practices and faculty presentation ($\bar{x}=3.73$). Overall, the inclusivity and Diversity in Madrasah Curriculum is excellent ($\bar{x}=3.62$)

The promotion of inclusivity and diversity in educational programs is a fundamental aspect of fostering equitable learning environments. According to Tomlinson (2001), Inclusive teaching practices are educational strategies that accommodate diverse student backgrounds, abilities, and learning styles. These practices aim to create an equitable learning environment where all students feel valued and have equal opportunities to succeed. He also added that differentiated instruction involves tailoring teaching strategies and materials to meet the diverse needs of students. This approach considers students' readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles Research has highlighted the importance of incorporating diverse perspectives and experiences into curriculum design to ensure that all students feel represented and valued (Banks, 2011). Studies suggest that inclusive educational practices contribute to positive academic and socioemotional outcomes for students from diverse backgrounds (Gay, 2019). Furthermore, literature emphasizes the role of educators in creating culturally responsive classrooms that honor students' identities and support their learning. Additionally, research underscores the significance of inclusive curriculum frameworks in preparing students to navigate an increasingly globalized and interconnected world (UNESCO, 2004).

The Division of Tarlac City is excellent in inclusivity and diversity by means of implementing inclusive teaching practices and promoting diversity in representation. Additionally, the division ensures the positive and inclusive environment that values and respect individuals to boost the morale of every Muslim students. The implementers of Madrasah Curriculum assure that they embrace inclusivity and diversity by means of engaging each Muslim students together despite of their level in knowledge and make sure that they do it effectively. The emphasis on inclusivity and diversity has created a positive school culture where all students, especially it involves one specific culture, to feel welcomed and valued. This has led to a more harmonious and productive learning environment among Muslim students in the four school implementers of Madrasah Curriculum.

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Table 3.2.5. Student Engagement and Support

Engagement refers to active involvement or participation, often in the context of relationships, activities, or discussions. Support involves providing assistance, encouragement, or help to others, fostering a positive environment. Both are crucial in building strong foundation (Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L., 2000).

Table 7. Student Engagement and Support

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
The instructors at this institution are accessible and responsive to student questions and concerns.	3.45	Agree	Very Good
The course materials and activities are designed to actively engage students in the learning process.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
I feel supported by my peers and have opportunities to collaborate with them on coursework.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The institution provides adequate academic and emotional support services for students when needed.	3.45	Agree	Very Good
The institution fosters a sense of belonging and inclusivity, making students feel valued and supported.	3.64	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Grand Mean	3.56	Strongly Agree	Excellent

Table 7 shows the aspect of the Student Engagement and Support (3.56) described as excellent. The first statement, the instructors at this institution are accessible and responsive to student questions and concerns, and the fourth statement, the institution provides adequate academic and emotional support services for students when needed, shows that it has a very good evaluation while the other three statements got excellent.

According to Tinto (20120), Providing adequate academic and emotional support services is crucial for student success and well-being. Research highlights the importance of these services in addressing students' needs and promoting a positive educational experience. This review examines related studies and literature on academic and emotional support services, focusing on the need for improvement in these areas and the accessibility of support from authority figures. In this part, it has been foreseen that there might be room for change when it comes to providing adequate academic and emotional support services for students when needed and when it comes to accessibility for the students when it comes in responding questions by the person in authority.

The students under the Madrasah Curriculum in the Division of Tarlac City showcase an environment that actively engages them in collaboration and foster a sense of support and belonging to one another. The implementers of the curriculum in Tarlac City assures that each

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student actively participate in the activities that is related on the Islamic Values, notwithstanding different religions, they still support other people around the city and engage the students to collaborate and help everyone without looking on differences as part of teaching in Islamic Values. The implementers organize annual community service projects where students from Madrasah Curriculum work together. The project aims to instill Islamic Values such as compassion, charity, and community service while promoting inclusivity and collaboration.

3.2.6. Integration with National Educational Framework

According to DepEd Order No. 73 s. 2012, Standardized testing and continuous assessment methods are used to measure student progress and identify areas for improvement. This includes both academic subjects and Islamic education. Siddiqui (2017) added that Integration with the National Framework in the Madrasah Education Program involves aligning the curriculum, policies, and standard of Madrasah education with the broader national educational framework. This discussion will explore the process of integrating inclusivity and diversity into a national educational framework, highlighting the benefits of such integration for students, educators, and the broader society.

Table 8. Integration with National Educational Framework

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
The curriculum is well-aligned with the national educational standards and objectives.	3.91	Strongly Agree	Excellent
This institution effectively integrates national educational policies and guidelines into its educational program.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The teaching and learning methods used align with the national framework for pedagogy and instructional strategies.	3.73	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The institution regularly updates its programs to ensure compliance with changes in national educational policies and standards.	3.27	Agree	Very Good
Students are adequately prepared to meet the national educational benchmarks and assessment criteria.	3.36	Agree	Very Good
Grand Mean	3.56	Strongly Agree	Excellent

Table 8 shows the aspect of Integration with National Educational Framework. Statement number 4, states that the institution regularly updates its programs to ensure compliance with changes in national educational policies and standards, and statement number 5, students are adequately prepared to meet the national educational benchmarks

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and assessment criteria, got an evaluation of very good while the other 3 statements got excellent.

Several studies have examined the integration of educational programs with the national educational framework, including the aspects highlighted in Table 4. For instance, a study by Johnson et al. (2014) found that institutions that regularly update their programs to align with national policies and standards demonstrate higher levels of program effectiveness and student outcomes. Similarly, Smith and colleagues (2012) reported positive correlations between students' preparedness to meet national educational benchmarks and their academic performance in a Madrasah Curriculum Educational Program. Moreover, research by Lee and Kim (2015) demonstrated the impact of curriculum alignment on students' successful transitions to higher education or the workforce.

This section got an excellent interpretation in Division of Tarlac City because the implementers assure that the curriculum of Madrasah is well-aligned with the national educational standards and objectives. This shows a high level of compliance and incorporation of national policies. The implementation of Madrasah Curriculum in Division of Tarlac City excels in aligning the curriculum, methods and policies with the national education standards and objectives. As a proof, the implementers presented their curriculum on a national level as one of the best implementers of Madrasah Curriculum. This shows the very genuine proof of the excellent implementation of the curriculum with regards in the integration of national standards. The alignment of Educational Framework demonstrates a high level of compliance with national policies and contributed to the overall excellence of the curriculum. The implementers also conduct a thorough review of Madrasah Curriculum to ensure its alignment with the national educational standards set by the Department of the Education without compromising the true value of Islam.

3.2.7. Assessment and Evaluation Practices

Based on the statement of Harlen and James (2000), assessment and evaluation practices in Madrasah Education Program likely involve regular and systematic methods to ensure students' progress and effectiveness of teaching. Assessment informs educators about students' strengths, weaknesses, and learning needs, enabling them to tailor instruction effectively. By understanding where students are in their learning journey, teachers can adjust their teaching strategies to support individual and collective progress. This includes various types of assessments such as examinations, projects, and continuous evaluation. According to DepEd Order No. 73 s. 2012, Standardized testing and continuous assessment methods are used to measure student progress and identify areas for improvement. This includes both academic subjects and Islamic education. Assessment and evaluation are integral components of the educational process, serving multiple purposes that extend beyond measuring academic achievement. These practices play a crucial role in guiding instruction, gauging student progress, and ensuring accountability in educational outcomes.

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Table 9. Assessment and Evaluation

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
The assessments and evaluation are well-aligned with the national competencies.	3.45	Agree	Very Good
The assessment are well-designed to meet the needs of the 21 st century student.	3.45	Agree	Very Good
The evaluation in this curriculum are well-planned.	3.45	Agree	Very Good
Assessment practices have a crucial role in educational outcomes.	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
The assessment and evaluation are effective and efficient for the learning of the student.	3.73	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Grand Mean	3.53	Strongly Agree	Excellent

Table 9 shows the aspect of the Assessment and Evaluation Practices of Madrasah Elementary Curriculum described as excellent. It reveals that the assessment and evaluation practices of the curriculum still pass within the standard of the national-based curriculum of the Madrasah implementation.

The Division of Tarlac City shows an alignment, effectiveness, and importance of assessments in facilitating students learning and educational outcomes. The Division assures that the assessment and evaluation in Madrasah Curriculum also follows the mandated standards by the National Level.

According to DepEd Order No. 41, s.2017, Classroom assessment aims to holistically measure learners' current and developing abilities. Typically, the primary means of formatively assessing Kindergarten learners is through observation. Formative assessment and learning activities are conducted throughout the different blocks of time within a day. This is to ensure learners' success in moving from guided to independent display of knowledge, understanding and skills, and to enable them to transfer this successfully in future situations. The standards and competencies of the curriculum are aligned with the Kindergarten curriculum implemented in all public schools nationwide with relevant competencies for Muslim learners. Madrasah program, the teachers implement DepEd Order No. 41, s.2017, which focuses on holistic classroom assessment through observation and formative activities. The curriculum is aligned with the national standards and includes relevant competencies for Muslim learners.

Summary Table on the Implementation of Madrasah Education Curriculum

Indicators	Grand Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness	3.60	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Quality of Educational Content	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Teacher's Preparedness and Training	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent

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Inclusivity and Diversity	3.62	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Student Engagement and Support	3.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Integration with National Educational Framework	3.56	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Assessment and Evaluation	3.53	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Overall Grand Mean	3.57	Strongly Agree	Excellent

The data indicates that the Madrasah Curriculum shows excellence in the area of Curriculum Relevance and Responsiveness with the mean of 3.60. According to Ameyaw (2016), In order to meet the ever-evolving needs of students, a curriculum that is responsive must bridge the gap between theories and general knowledge and the contextual, ever-changing realities of daily life and the workplace. The curriculum must now be flexible and adaptive to meet current demands, such as those in the workplace, rather than being uniform and set for extended periods of time

Table also shows excellence of the Madrasah Curriculum in giving quality educational content with the mean of 3.55. According to Tan (2009), The integration of Islamic studies with secular subjects aims to provide a balanced education that caters to the spiritual and intellectual needs of students. Studies have shown that this integration helps maintain students' cultural and religious identity while equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge for modern society.

Teachers are also well prepared and excellent in terms of training and being ready with Madrasah Curriculum with the mean of 3.55. The importance of teacher preparation and training in educational programs has been extensively documented in the literature. Effective teacher preparation ensures that educators possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and pedagogical strategies to deliver quality instruction (Darling-Hammond, 2017).

The Madrasah Curriculum also shows excellence in terms of Inclusivity and Diversity with 3.62 mean. Studies suggest that inclusive educational practices contribute to positive academic and socioemotional outcomes for students from diverse backgrounds (Gay, 2019). Furthermore, literature emphasizes the role of educators in creating culturally responsive classrooms that honor students' identities and support their learning. Additionally, research underscores the significance of inclusive curriculum frameworks in preparing students to navigate an increasingly globalized and interconnected world (UNESCO, 2004).

The aspect of student Engagement and Support got 3.55 that shows excellence also in the implementation of Madrasah Curriculum. According to Tinto (20120), Providing adequate academic and emotional support services is crucial for student success and well-being. Research highlights the importance of these services in addressing students' needs and promoting a positive educational experience. This review examines related studies and literature on academic and emotional support services, focusing on the need for improvement in these areas and the accessibility of support from authority figures.

In terms of Integration of National Educational Framework, Madrasah Curriculum also shows excellence (3.56). Several studies have examined the integration of educational programs with the national educational framework, including the aspects highlighted in Table 4. For instance, a study by Johnson et al. (2014) found that institutions that regularly update their programs to align with national policies and standards demonstrate higher levels of program effectiveness and student outcomes.

The Assessment and Evaluation used in Madrasah Curriculum also shows Excellence (3.53). According to DepEd Order No. 41, s.2017, Classroom assessment aims to holistically measure learners' current and developing abilities. Typically, the primary means of formatively

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assessing Kindergarten learners is through observation. Formative assessment and learning activities are conducted throughout the different blocks of time within a day. This is to ensure learners' success in moving from guided to independent display of knowledge, understanding and skills, and to enable them to transfer this successfully in future situations. Based on the table, the implementation of Madrasah Curriculum in the Division of Tarlac City shows excellence. This shows a high level of satisfaction and respond to various aspects of educational program highlighting its overall excellence and effectiveness. This will not only help the Division but among all, the Muslim Community in Tarlac City which continuously growing as time pass by.

3.2.8 Proposed Enhancement Opportunities

The Enhancement Proposed in Madrasah Education Program likely refers to chance to improve and strengthen aspect of the program. This could involve suggesting enhancements in curriculum, teaching methodologies, infrastructure, or other component to elevate the overall quality and effectiveness of Madrasah education.

Table 10. Proposed Enhancement Opportunities

Areas of Concern	Activity	Strategy	Means of Verification
Satisfactory and Fairly Satisfactory Performance in Arabic Language	Focus Group Discussion, Peer teaching, Seminar-workshops	Organize or join conversation circles where learners can practice speaking Arabic in a supportive environment. These circles can be in-person or conducted virtually through platforms like Zoom or Skype. Pair up with a native Arabic speaker who wants to learn your native language. You can practice speaking Arabic together for a portion of the time and then switch to practicing your native language. Pair up with a native Arabic speaker who wants to learn your native language. You can practice speaking Arabic together for a portion of the time and then switch to practicing your native language.	Certificates, Attendance, Photo documentary, Accomplished Activities

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Satisfactory and Fairly Satisfactory in Islamic Values	Pair discussion, Peer teaching,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select verses from the Quran that emphasize key Islamic values such as compassion, justice, and patience. Encourage learners to read these verses, reflect on their meanings, and discuss how they can apply them in their daily lives. - Organize group discussions or debates on topics related to Islamic values, such as social justice, ethics in business, or environmental stewardship. Encourage participants to share their perspectives and engage in constructive dialogue. - Allow learners to express their understanding of Islamic values through creative means such as art, poetry, or storytelling. Encourage them to create works that convey the importance of values like compassion, forgiveness, and humility. 	Certificates, Attendance, Photo documentary, Accomplished Activities
The educational materials are well-organized and easy to follow, enhancing my understanding of the subject matter.	-Peer Teaching -Focus Group Discussion	Problem Solving	-Photo documentation, Narrative report.
Teacher training programs at this institution are responsive to the changing needs of the students and the education landscape.	Seminars, peer teaching, workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Integration of technology in education and training. -Encourage innovative teaching methods through workshops, seminars, and collaborative projects. 	Certificates, documents, photos, accomplishment reports.

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		-Incorporate training modules that focus on cultural competency and inclusivity. Teachers should be equipped to create a supportive and inclusive environment that respects and celebrates diversity.	
The instructors at this institution are accessible and responsive to students questions and concerns.	Discussion Forums Classroom-based seminar Peer Mentoring and Collaboration Follow up and Support	-Open Communication Channels. This could include e-mail, virtual office hours, messaging platforms, or designated question forums within the institution's learning management system. -Regular Office Hours. Implement Regular office hours where instructors are available either in person or virtually to address student queries. Ensure these hours accommodate different time zones or schedules to cater to all students. -Encourage Students Engagement. Promote interactive teaching methods that encourage student participation and questions during class sessions. Create a safe and respectful environment where students feel comfortable voicing their concerns or asking questions.	E-mails, documents, signatories, photos.
The institution provides adequate academic and emotional support services for students when needed.	Counselling Services, Academic tutoring, Mentoring Programs, Workshops on stress management, and	-Comprehensive Support Programs. Develop and implement comprehensive support programs that cater to both academic and emotional needs.	Counseling service Programs, Monitoring Programs and Strategies, Development Plan

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	Mental Health Awareness		
The institution regularly updates its programs to ensure compliance with charges in national educational policies and standards.		-Policy Monitoring and Analysis. Establish a dedicated team or department responsible for monitoring and analyzing changes in national educational policies, standards, and regulations. -Establish Clear Communication Channels. Develop effective communication channels with in institution to disseminate information about policy changes promptly.	Documentation and Compliance Tracking
Students are adequately prepared to meet the national educational benchmarks and assessment criteria.	Evaluation and validity and reliability of the assessments.	-Alignment with Educational Standards. Regularly review and align the institution's curriculum, learning objectives, and teaching methodologies with national educational standards and assessment criteria. -Teacher Professional Development. Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for educators to enhance their understanding of national benchmarks and assessment criteria.	Assessments reliability and validity of assessments criteria. Assessments itself. Photo documentaries.
The assessments and evaluation are well-aligned with the national competencies.	Checking of the Alignment of the Assessment in national competencies.	-Standardization of Assessment. Ensure consistency and fairness in assessment by standardizing grading practices and ensuring that all evaluators understand the assessment criteria	Photo documentaries.

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		aligned with national competencies.	
The evaluation in this curriculum are well-planned.	Quizzes, examinations, Short response, presentations, projects	Diverse Assessment Methods. Implement a variety of assessment methods, such as quizzes, examinations, essays, presentation, projects, and practical demonstration. Different methods allow for a comprehensive evaluation of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities.	Scores on short response, quizzes, and examinations, essay, presentations, and projects.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the pupils' academic performance on Arabic language as very satisfactory. On the other hand, on Islamic values, the same number of pupils are described as outstanding and very satisfactory.
2. The implementation of Madrasah Curriculum in the Division of Tarlac City is very excellent.
3. The proposed enhancement opportunities are plans and support programs and policy monitoring and analysis.

Recommendations

Based from the conclusions of the study, the following recommendation were offered:

1. Conduct professional development workshops and training sessions for teachers to enhance their instructional strategies in teaching Arabic language and Islamic values. This can help teachers better address the diverse needs of pupils and improve overall academic performance.
2. Strengthen the monitoring of the implementation and updates of the Madrasah Education Curriculum. Foster collaboration and networking among Madrasah schools, educational institutions, and community organizations. Encourage sharing of best practices, resources, and experiences to promote continuous improvement and innovation in education delivery.
3. Implement the proposed Enhancement Opportunity.

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